

D4.3 CHARACTERIZATION OF INPUT MATERIAL, BENCHMARKING OF CLEANING PROCESSES WORK PACKAGE 4

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T4.2: Analytical characterization and
monitoring of recycling process quality
and recycling products

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PUBLISHABLE EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

One of the main tasks of Work Package (WP) 4 comprises the analytical characterization and monitoring of recyclates' quality at different stages of the recycling process. This is essential as the quality of the input materials as well as the performed recycling treatments (such as deodorization, water-based de-inking, solvent-based process) are assumed to have a significant impact on the presence of migratable components in the recyclate material produced within the project.

For the assessment of quality, the chromatographic fingerprint of the various recyclates as well as of various waste samples was characterized by screening techniques (such as Headspace GC-MS, GC-FID/MS with liquid injection, HPLC-HRMS) and (semi-)quantification of residual contents. Furthermore, the content of inorganic components in the material as a marker for the fate of pigment and tracer substances was performed by ICP-MS. In addition to the instrumental analyses, the presence of mutagenic substances in the recyclates must be excluded since mutagenicity is regarded as the most critical toxicological parameter. This was done using AMES-based bioassays.

From the analyses performed on three different waste samples as an input material, it could be concluded that the samples contain a high amount of both saturated and unsaturated hydrocarbons as well as a variety of volatile, semi-volatile and non-volatile contaminants. In addition, mutagenicity was observed by bioassays. It was concluded based on the experiments that the quality of the PE waste samples must improve significantly for the use in food contact applications.

In the investigated samples of different recycling steps, a range of different contaminants was detected in addition to chemical compounds typically found in laminate structures. The results of these analyses are used to set up a database as reported in Deliverable 4.5. Furthermore, the (semi-)quantification results on substances contained in the recycled material serve as a basis to calculate the theoretical migration into food taking into account the barrier properties of the laminate structure as evaluated within Task 4.5. This is reported in Deliverable 4.6.

Using biological assays, mutagenicity was observed in the sample after recycling (100 % Project PCR monofilm from Loop3 Cycle1), which is in line with literature data.

Inorganic pigments based on copper and titanium were selected as marker substances for the used printing inks. The removal of these elements was the basis to assess the capability of the investigated CIRCULAR FoodPack treatment steps and technologies to remove printing ink components. By ICP-MS measurements, the obtained data on the reduction efficiencies showed that the investigated treatment steps and technologies are not yet sufficient to achieve the envisaged > 99.5 % ink removal (based on the investigated inorganic elements as representative printing ink components).

ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	
CAD	Charged aerosol detector
FID	Flame ionization detection
GC-FID	Gas chromatography
HPLC	High performance liquid chromatography
HR	High resolution
IAS	Intentionally added substances
ICP-MS	Inductively coupled plasma - mass spectrometry
LC	Liquid chromatography
MS	Mass spectrometry / mass spectrometric detection
MOAH	Mineral oil aromatic hydrocarbons
MOSH	Mineral oil saturated hydrocarbons
NIAS	Non-intentionally added substances
PCR	Post-consumer recyclates
PE	Polyethylene
POSH	Polyolefin oligomeric saturated hydrocarbons
WP	Work package

1. INTRODUCTION

The main objective of work package (WP) 4 is to define, evaluate and assess innovative recycling strategies and newly developed packaging structures for the use of recycled polyethylene in flexible packaging for food and personal care applications.

For this purpose, analytical migration and compliance testing are applied in order to assess and ensure food regulatory compliance of the laminate structures developed within this project.

As the quality of the input material and the envisaged recycling steps are assumed to have a significant impact on the presence of migratable components in the recyclate material produced within the project, the aim of Task 4.2 is to characterize input waste and to analytically monitor the different envisaged recycling treatments and production processes (deodorization, water-based de-inking) in order to substantially improve the quality level of recycled PE.

The focus is set on comparative studies of subsequent treatment steps in order to define substances that are either still present, reduced or are newly formed during subsequent treatment steps up to the final project recyclate.

The results obtained from the instrumental analysis shall be combined with the outcome of bioassay tests, which shall be used to prove the absence of mutagenic substances as described in Task 4.2.

The outcome of these tests allowed to conclude on the suitability of the recycling treatments and combinations thereof as developed in WP3 in order to produce laminates with recyclates for food packaging / personal care applications (WP5).

2. CHARACTERIZATIONS OF THE INPUT MATERIAL / WASTE

a. Sample material

For the analytical characterization work to be done on real waste samples, samples collected in France, Belgium and Germany were sorted into different sub-fractions, i.e. “food” and “non-foods” by WP2 and were provided to WP4 in the form of shredded, washed flakes. From these flake samples, 10 different samples were analyzed by means of Headspace GC-MS screening analysis by Fraunhofer IVV to decide on the samples that shall subsequently be used for an in-depth characterization. A representative GC-MS chromatogram of sample CFP00164 – Belgian Food is presented in Figure 1. Based on this screening by Fraunhofer, 3 samples were selected that can be considered ‘worst-case’ in terms of number and chemical diversity of volatile molecules detected (see Table 1).

Table 1: Waste samples analysed and selected for further characterization

Nestlé code	SLIMS	CFP number	Sample Description	Selected for in depth Characterisation
		Washed Flakes		
PIRM00091		CFP00164	Belgium Food	X
		CFP00165	Belgium Non-Food	
		CFP00166	Germany Food 323-2	
		CFP00167	Germany Non-Food 323-2	
		CFP00168	Germany Food 310	
PIRM00092		CFP00169	Germany Non-food 310	X
		CFP00170	Germany Food 352	
		CFP00171	Germany Non-Food 352	
		CFP00172	France mixed	
PIRM00093		CFP00173	Germany mixed	X

Figure 1: Exemplary Headspace GC-MS chromatogram of sample CFP00164 – Belgian Food

A representative picture of the investigated washed flake samples is shown in Figure 2, it has a project internal code of CFP00164.

Figure 2: The investigated washed flake samples (representative picture of CFP00164)

In meetings of the WP4 partners Fraunhofer and NESTLE, potential extraction methods and analytical techniques for the analyses of the three selected samples were discussed. It was agreed to focus on the following analyses / parameters:

- **Saturated and unsaturated hydrocarbons (incl. mineral oils and POSH) by composition using LCGC-FID.**
- **Screening of chemical composition by headspace GC-MS, GC-MS/FID and LC-HRMS/CAD.**
- **Screening of extracts with biological assays.**

b. Mineral oils by composition using LCGC-FID

Saturated and unsaturated hydrocarbons which includes mineral oils and POSH (Polyolefin saturated hydrocarbons) were screened in the 3 waste samples by LCGC-FID. The method used was based on an internal Nestlé method that analyses hydrocarbons from polyolefins by extraction for 2 hours in hexane/ethanol at room temperature. After extraction, water was added to the hexane/ethanol to separate the hexane fraction from the ethanol/water. The hexane fraction was injected on LCGC-FID for analysis of saturated and unsaturated hydrocarbons. The method is aligned with current protocols in place by JRC.¹

Representative chromatograms for the LCGC-FID analysis focusing on saturated and unsaturated hydrocarbons are given in Figure 3 for the representative sample PIRM00091 (Belgian food grade, CFP000164).

¹ JRC technical reports 'Guidance on sampling, analysis and data reporting for the monitoring of mineral oil hydrocarbons in food and food contact materials'. S. Bratinova, E. Hoekstra 2019

The results of the analysis in Table 2 below indicate that all three investigated samples contain a high amount of both saturated and unsaturated hydrocarbons. The saturated hydrocarbons are likely attributed to the presence of polyolefin oligomer saturated hydrocarbon (POSH). However, there is also a likelihood that MOSH and MOAH are present, as evidenced by the detection of a hump in the MOAH fraction, see chromatograms below. This hump aligns with the hump observed in the MOSH fraction, which further suggests the presence of mineral oils. To confirm whether the samples contain only POSH or also MOSH and/or MOAH, it is recommended to perform a confirmation analysis using 2-dimensional GC-MS.

Table 2: Mineral oils by composition using LCGC-FID:

Nestle sample ID	Fraunhofer sample ID	Saturated hydrocarbons (mg/kg)	Unsaturated hydrocarbons (mg/kg)
PIRM00091	Belgian food grade, CFP000164	1265	182
PIRM00092	German non-food grade (310) CFP00169	3074	556
PIRM00093	German mixed origin, CFP00173	2444	606

Figure 3: Chromatogram of saturated (left) and unsaturated hydrocarbons (right) obtained for PIRM00091 (Belgian food grade, CFP000164)

c. Screening of chemical composition of PE waste by headspace GC-MS, GC-MS/FID and LC-HRMS/CAD.

Comparison Fraunhofer and Nestlé sample preparation procedure

As both Fraunhofer and Nestlé have in-house analytical protocols to screen for the composition of recycled plastics, it was decided to compare sample preparation methods by overlaying chromatograms before screening the three waste samples in detail.

The flake samples were cryomilled at Fraunhofer IVV and a portion of the cryomilled samples was provided to Nestlé. In addition, the cryomilled samples were extracted with organic solvents according to procedures established at Nestlé and Fraunhofer. For the extraction performed at Fraunhofer 0.5 g of cryomilled flakes were extracted with 20 ml hexane/acetone (according to the protocol proposed by Nestlé) and with 20 ml hexane/ethanol (Fraunhofer protocol). An aliquot of the extracts was also sent to Nestlé for the comparison study. In short, the Nestlé sample preparation protocol was by extracting 2 gram of the recycled resin in 40 mL of hexane/acetone for 16 hours at room temperature. The extract was concentrated 10 times before analysis by GC-MS/FID. For analysis by LC-HRMS/CAD, the extract was evaporated under a gentle nitrogen flow and reconstituted in acetonitrile: water (7:3) prior to the analysis.

The figures below show the result between the sample preparation of Fraunhofer versus the sample preparation of Nestlé for sample PIRM00093 (German mixed origin, CFP00173).

Figure 4: Comparison of chromatogram of hexane/acetone (top) and hexane/ethanol (bottom) extract prepared by Fraunhofer for PIRM00093. Analysis of the two extracts was performed by GC-MS/FID by Nestlé.

Figure 5: Comparison of chromatogram of hexane/acetone (top) and hexane/ethanol (bottom) extract prepared by Fraunhofer for PIRM00093. Analysis of the two extracts was performed by LC-HRMS/CAD by Nestlé.

Globally, the same compounds were extracted by both sample preparation procedures. The impact on the result was considered limited for the purpose of this investigation. As further experiments were performed by Nestlé, it was decided to proceed with the Nestlé protocol (extraction with hexane/acetone).

Figure 6 shows the GC-MS chromatogram obtained when the extracts were prepared by Nestlé (top) and Fraunhofer (bottom) for PIPM00093 using the Nestlé sample preparation procedure. The difference in intensity between the extracts was due to an additional concentration factor of 10 applied by Nestlé. As the concentrated extract revealed more information, it was decided to perform further investigations with the Nestlé sample preparation procedure. The LC-HRMS-CAD chromatogram was not further evaluated for these two samples due to this large difference in intensity observed by GC-MS.

Figure 6: Comparison of chromatogram of hexane/acetone extract for PIRM00093 prepared by Nestlé (top) and Fraunhofer (bottom). Analysis of the two extracts was performed by GC-MS/FID by Nestlé.

Chemical composition of the three PE waste samples

The chemical composition of the three samples was analysed by headspace GC-MS, GC-MS/FID and LC-HRMS. The GC-MS chromatograms below show the difference between the three samples. The main question of this task was to understand the difference in the chemical composition between PE waste from food contact material origin and PE waste from non-food contact origin. Therefore, only samples PIRM00091 and PIRM00092 were further investigated for a detailed chemical composition (see three tables below). Note that the identification was not based on chemical standards, but on commercially available libraries and in-house libraries. Hence, the confidence in identification varies between the different molecules reported. In the database (Task 4.4) to be delivered at later stage the confidence in identification will be reported. A detailed list of chemicals is not provided here as it will be part of Task 4.4.

Table 3: Results volatiles molecules detected by Headspace GC-MS

Nestle sample ID	Fraunhofer sample ID	Tentative identities of volatiles detected
PIRM00091	Belgian food grade, CFP000164	70 substances detected. Substances of list B of Swiss printing inks ordinance Styrene Caprolactam Short chain aldehydes Alkylated furans
PIRM00092	German non-food grade (310) CFP00169	29 substances detected. substances of list B of Swiss printing inks ordinance Short chain aldehydes

Table 4: Results semi-volatiles molecules detected by GC-MS/FID

Nestle sample ID	Fraunhofer sample ID	Tentative identities of semi-volatiles detected
PIRM00091	Belgian food grade, CFP000164	143 substances detected: Substances of list B of Swiss printing inks ordinance Caprolactam Trimer of Styrene Allowed phthalates Cyclic polyester oligomers Biocide
PIRM00092	German non-food grade (310) CFP00169	141 substances detected: Substances of list B of Swiss printing inks ordinance Trimer of Styrene POSH Allowed phthalates Chlorinated phosphate Flame retardant UV lightfilter (from cosmetics) Fungicide Suspected EDC

Table 5: Results non-volatiles molecules detected by LC-HRMS/CAD

Nestle sample ID	Fraunhofer sample ID	Tentative identities of non-volatiles detected
PIRM00091	Belgian food grade, CFP000164	152 substances detected: Substances of list B of Swiss printing inks ordinance Caffeine/piperine Cyclic polyester/polyamide oligomers Allowed + non-allowed phthalates Bisphenol S and bisphenol B Biocide
PIRM00092	German non-food grade (310) CFP00169	154 substances detected: Substances of list B of Swiss printing inks ordinance Caffeine/piperine Cyclic polyester/polyamide oligomers Various pigments Allowed + non-allowed phthalates Bisphenol S and bisphenol B Drug to treat fungal infections Biocide Fungicide Insecticide

Figure 7: Comparison of chromatogram by GC-MS/FID of hexane/acetone extract for the three PE waste samples selected. Analysis was performed by Nestlé.

d. Screening of extracts with biological assays

The same extract in hexane/acetone obtained above following the Nestlé sample preparation procedure was used for testing with bioassays (AMES and endocrine activity Calux) aligned with the procedure typically applied by OFI². 1.5 mL of the concentrated hexane/acetone extract was mixed with 1.5 mL DMSO (dimethylsulfoxide). The hexane/acetone was removed under a gentle nitrogen flow until the 1.5 mL DMSO remained. The DMSO residue was used for testing with the bioassays.

Ames test was performed on the DMSO extracts with Strains TA98 and TA100 with and without metabolic activation (S9) by Gentronix Ltd. (UK, Cheshire). One sample (PIRM00092) was clearly positive (Strain TA98 without metabolic activation) indicating presence of mutagenic compounds. The two other samples were most likely positive for this condition as well, but this could not be concluded with 100 % certainty due to a contamination issue from the lab. These results are fully in-line with research results for mechanically recycled polyolefins².

² Mayrhofer et al. Safety assessment of recycled Plastics from post-consumer waste with a combination of a miniaturized Ames test and chromatographic analysis. *Recycling* 2023, 8, 87.

Table 6: Ames test results on extracts from the three packaging waste samples.

Nestle sample ID	Fraunhofer sample ID	Strain TA98 -S9	Strain TA98 +S9	Strain TA100 -S9	Strain TA100 +S9
PIRM00091	Belgian food grade, FP000164	Likely positive	Negative	Inconclusive	Inconclusive
PIRM00092	German non-food grade (310) CFP00169	Positive	Negative	Negative	Negative
PIRM00093	German mixed origin, CFP00173	Likely positive	Negative	Inconclusive	Inconclusive

Endocrine activity was measured using the (anti-)ER α Calux, (anti-AR Calux) and cell viability (RealTime-glo) assays. The same DMSO extracts as tested for mutagenicity with Ames were used for this purpose. Positive results were obtained for ER α and Anti-AR. Anti-ER α and AR were negative for all samples (Table 7).

Especially the positive AMES test raises a concern if the recyclates of these post-consumer waste materials would be used in food contact applications (e.g. Article 3 of the Framework Regulation (EC) No 1935/2004 would be impacted).

Table 7: Endocrine activity results on extracts from the three packaging waste samples.

Nestle sample ID	Fraunhofer sample ID	ER	Anti-ER α	AR	Anti-AR
PIRM00091	Belgian food grade, FP000164	Inconclusive	Negative	Negative	Positive
PIRM00092	German non-food grade (310) CFP00169	Positive	Negative	Negative	Inconclusive
PIRM00093	German mixed origin, CFP00173	Positive	Negative	Negative	Negative

3. CHARACTERIZATION AND MONITORING OF RECYCLATES' QUALITY THROUGH THE RECYCLING AND RE-USE PROCESS STEPS

In order to characterize and monitor the quality of the recyclate through the different recycling treatments, sample material originating from different steps of the recycling cascade of Loop 3 – Cycle 1 was provided by the respective project partners to WP4 for analysis. The sample flow is given in the picture below (Figure 9) and reflects mainly water-based deinking, drying, densification, mechanical recycling, deodorization and production of films with 100 % use of recycled resin. The material was shared between the WP4 partners Fraunhofer and Nestlé. In total, 13 samples in the overview below were identified as relevant for the individual / essential cascade steps.

The following samples have to be highlighted: CFP00219, which represents the starting point of the cascade and sample CFP00241 representing the 100 % project PCR film that has been used behind the functional barrier(s) in the laminate structure. This sample also marks the endpoint of the applied recycling cascade (1st cycle of Loop3). Consequently, special attention for the discussion of results in terms of chromatographic analysis and compound identification in this Deliverable is centered around these two samples.

Figure 8: Sample CFP00241 (Monofilm 100 % project recyclate of Loop 3 Cycle 1)

Figure 9: Sample flow of Loop 3 – Cycle 1 cascade

The samples were analysed using the following analytical approaches:

- Headspace GC-MS (Fraunhofer)
- GC-FID/MS with liquid extraction (Fraunhofer / Nestlé)
- ICP-MS (Fraunhofer)
- LC-HR-MS (Nestlé)
- Saturated/unsaturated hydrocarbons incl mineral oils (Nestlé)
- Bioassays (Nestlé)

These experiments were set up to cover the full molecular weight range of substances up to 1000 Da. It is conventionally assumed that components with a molecular mass of above 1000 Dalton (Da) are very unlikely to be absorbed by the gastro-intestinal tract³.

a. Headspace GC-MS analysis for volatile components (Fraunhofer)

The analysis was qualitative only and was performed with a Headspace-GC/MS of Shimadzu:

GCMS-QP2020 NX coupled with a Shimadzu HS-20 headspace autosampler

Oven temperature:	120 °C
Equilibration time:	60 min
Sample line temperature:	150 °C
Transfer line temperature:	150 °C
Pressure build-up time:	0.50 min

³ EFSA CEF Panel, (EFSA Panel on Food Contact Materials, Enzymes, Flavourings and Processing Aids), 2008. Note for guidance for the preparation of an application for the safety assessment of a substance to be used in plastic food contact materials. EFSA J. 6 (7), 21r, 41 pp. (Amended: 18 May 2023)

Load Time:	0.50 min
Injection time:	0.06 min
Column:	Rxi®-624 Sil MS, length 30 m; inner diameter 0.25 mm; 1.4 µm film thickness
Temperature program:	35 °C (6 min) - rate 5 °C/min up to 120 °C (0min) - rate 10 °C/min up to 260 °C (10 min)
Carrier gas:	Helium
Ion source temperature:	200 °C
MS conditions:	El Ionization, mass range m/z 40-450 Dalton

The identification of the mass spectra was done with an automated search by comparison with an internal mass spectra library (Fraunhofer IVV, Rxi624-Library v2).

The chromatogram of the 100 % project PCR (sample CFP00241) is given in Figure 10. Alkanes, aldehydes and organic solvents were detected as the main headspace components (Table 8).

As a comparison, Figure 11 shows the chromatogram of a commercial PCR (CFP00242, non-food grade⁴). Compared to the project PCR, the signal intensities were higher. The main components were identified as the alkanes decane ($R_t = 22.5$ min), dodecane ($R_t = 28.1$ min), tetradecane ($R_t = 31.8$ min), hexadecane ($R_t = 34.7$) as well as acetic acid ($R_t = 9.0$ min).

Figure 10: Headspace GC-MS chromatogram of sample CFP00241 (100 % project PCR)

⁴ Recycl-IN rLL9610, Ineos Olefins & Polymers Europe (granulate provided by Amcor)

Figure 11: Headspace GC-MS chromatogram of sample CFP00242 (commercial PCR granulate)

Table 8: Identification of headspace components in sample CFP00241; marked in green: low volatiles, blue: medium volatiles (according to retention time); highlighted: main fingerprint components (based on area comparison)

Retention time	Identification / characterization
1.6	1-Propene, 2-methyl- (CAS 115-11-7)
1.7	Ethene, ethoxy- (CAS 109-92-2)
2.9	Acetic acid ethenyl ester (CAS 108-05-4)
4.5	n-Hexane (CAS 110-54-3)
5.6	Butanal (CAS 123-72-8)
10.7	Pentanal (CAS 110-62-3)
15.6	Hexanal (CAS 66-25-1)
26.8	Nonanal (CAS 124-19-6)
28.1	Dodecane (CAS 112-40-3)
31.7	Tetradecane (CAS 629-59-4)
34.7	Hexadecane (CAS 544-76-3)
37.2	Octadecane (CAS 593-45-3)
38.6	Phosphoric acid, tris(2-ethylhexyl) ester (CAS 78-42-2)

b. GC-FID/MS analysis for semi-volatile components (Fraunhofer)

1 g of the samples (in duplicate) was extracted with 10 ml dichloromethane (DCM) for 4 days at 40 °C by total immersion. An internal standard of butylated hydroxyanisole (BHA) und Tinuvin 234 was added to an aliquot of the extracts and analysed by gas chromatography with flame ionisation detection (GC-FID) for semi-volatile compounds.

The extracts were analysed by gas chromatography with flame ionisation detection (GC-FID): DB-1-capillary column (length 30 m, inner diameter 0.25 mm, film thickness 0.25 µm) and the following temperature program: 50 °C (2 min isotherm) up to 340 °C with a heating rate of 10 °C/min, then 10 min isotherm at 340 °C. Peaks of interest were semi-quantified using the internal standard BHA.

This method is valid for organic components with a molecular weight of approx. 150 to 700 Dalton.

The identification of the main compounds was done by GC analysis coupled with mass spectrometry. GC/MS-System: ThermoFinnigan SSQ, column: Optima-5-MS - 30 m length - 0.25 mm i.d. - 0.25 μm film thickness, temperature program: 50 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (2 min), heating rate 10 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ min⁻¹, 340 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (30 min), full scan mode, mass range m/z 40 - 800.

The identification of the spectra was done by comparison with the NIST spectra library (NIST/EPA/NIH Mass Spectral library, Version 2.3, 2017). A confirmation of the suggested spectra by analysis of a respective standard was not done.

Figure 12: GC-FID gas chromatogram of the concentrated DCM extract of sample CFP00241 (100 % project recycle, Loop 3 Cycle 1)

Figure 13: GC-FID gas chromatogram of the concentrated DCM extract of sample CFP00242 (commercial PCR granulate)

Table 9: Identification of fingerprint components in the 100 % project recycle sample CFP00241

Peak	Identification / characterisation	Semi-Quantification results in µg/g
1	Alkane C16	10
2	Alkane C18	24
5	Methylpalmitate CAS 112-39-0	57
6	Stearic acid CAS 57-11-4	21
7	Alkane C20	25
8	Hexadecanol CAS 36653-82-4 or structurally related alcohol	94
9	Methylstearate CAS 112-61-8	42
10	Alkane C22	23
11	Probably carbonic acid amide	13
12	Alkane or alcohol	36
13	Alkane C24	25
14	not identified, no mass spectrum available	18
15	Alkane C26	17
19	Alkane C28	14
20	Alkane C30	13
21	Alkane C32	13
22	Tris-(2,4-di-tert-butylphenyl)-phosphite (CAS: 31570-04-4, trade name: e.g. Irgafos 168)	968
23	oxidised form of Irgafos 168	2102

The detection limit (dl) was 1 µg/g.

c. GC-MS/FID and LC-HRMS/CAD (Nestlé)

The methods applied concern in-house developed suspect-targeted and non-targeted screening methods for migrating substances. The methods are based on liquid injection GC-MS-FID and LC-HRMS/CAD. Below, a short summary of the methods is provided.

To prepare extracts for analysis by GC-MS and LC-HRMS, 2 g of the packaging sample was extracted in 40 mL of hexane/acetone at room temperature for 16 hours in duplicate. The extract was concentrated 10 times.

The concentrated extract was injected on GC-MS/FID (7890B GC system with FID and 5975C inert GC/MSD, Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA) operated with a Rxi-5MS column (Restek 13423-6850, BGB Analytik AG, Boeckten, Switzerland). Detection of extracted compounds was performed with MS for identification and FID for semi-quantification. Identification was performed using NIST (NIST20, W12MAIN) and various in-house libraries. An alkane mixture of C7 and C40 (49452-U, C7 - C40 Saturated Alkanes Standard, Supelco, Sigma Aldrich, Buchs, Switzerland) was analysed to record retention indices (semi-standard non-polar) that facilitate identification of extracted molecules. The reconstituted extract was analysed with a Thermo Orbitrap Q-Exactive detector (Thermo Fisher Scientific, San José, CA, USA) for identification and a Charged Aerosol Detector (CAD) (Corona Veo RS, Thermo Fisher Scientific, San José, CA, USA) for semi-quantification. A UV-DAD detector (DAD, Ultimate 300RS, Thermo Fisher Scientific, San José, CA, USA) was operated in parallel to support proposed identities of molecules. Identification by LC-HRMS was performed using on-line libraries (mzCloud) and an internally developed library consisting of molecules measured but also a suspect list of molecules.

All samples from Figure 9 were screened for NIAS (non-intentionally added substances) using GC-MS/FID with the aim to visualize the appearance and removal of contaminants throughout the recycling process. Figure 14 shows the chromatograms for these samples.

The chromatograms show that during the various recycling steps of samples CFP00219, 216, 217, 220, 234 (deinking, drying, densification, additivation, granulation and deodorisation) the more volatile substances are efficiently removed as this is evidenced by the decrease of number and intensity of peaks at low retention time. From sample CFP00243 an intense substance is detected around 41 min and a few molecules at low retention time. This is because samples CFP00243/244/245 are not related to samples CFP00219-241 and have therefore another chemical composition.

Based on these preliminary tests it was decided to perform a full identification of substances in the extracts of the samples listed below:

- CFP00219. This sample was made of shredded input laminates going into the recycling process and manufacturing of the new structure holding recycled content. Note that these input laminates were in contact with coffee.
- CFP00241. This sample was a monofilm (100 %) produced from CFP00219 subjected to various recycling steps (deinking, drying, densification, additivation, granulation and deodorisation).

Figure 14: GC-MS profiles of all samples tested.

A comparison of the project PCR (PIRM00655) and commercial PCR (PIRM00656) was made with a representative virgin LDPE that was not directly linked to the current project. The figure below (Figure 15) shows the chromatograms obtained by GC-MS and LC-HRMS (positive ion mode).

The GC-MS chromatogram clearly shows that the virgin LDPE is less complex in terms of chemical composition. This is evidenced by the many overlapping peaks for the project PCR and commercial PCR, whereas the virgin LDPE has much less overlap. In addition, the baselines of the project and commercial PCR are clearly increased due to the presence of POSH formed during use/recycling and many other compounds present that are typically not found in food packaging.

The LC-HRMS chromatograms show clearly the purity of the virgin LDPE that contains an intense signal for an antioxidant. The project and commercial PCR are significantly more complex due to presence of various contaminants.

Figure 15: Chromatograms of GC-MS (top) and LC-HRMS analysis (bottom) of project PCR (PIRM00655) and commercial PCR (PIRM00656) and virgin PE

A full summary of the substances that were detected and further discussion is presented in Deliverable 4.5 “Database of contaminants in recycled polyolefins”. Semi-quantification was performed with detectors and external standards described in the experimental section.

Identification was performed but not confirmed for all molecules with analytical standards. Most of the identifications should therefore be considered as ‘tentative’. By LC, the Schymanski index⁵ indicates whether the identification is good (1) or bad (5). A similar scale was developed for GC

⁵ Schymanski et al. Identifying small molecules via High resolution mass spectrometry: Communicating confidence. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 2014, Jan 29, 2097-2098.

(GC confidence index) where A indicates a good identification and E a highly tentative identification.

Table 10: GC-MS/FID data of molecules detected in sample PIRM00651 (CFP00219) entering the mechanical recycling / processing cascade

DB-5 RI	CAS	Chemical name	Exact Mol. Weight	Molecular formula	GC Confidence Index	µg/g material
1490		BHA external standard				
962	100-52-7	Benzaldehyde	106,042	C7H6O	A	2,33
985	98-83-9	.alpha.-Methylstyrene	118,078	C9H10	B	33,78
1004	111-90-0	Ethanol, 2-(2-ethoxyethoxy)-	134,094	C6H14O3	B	4,64
1072	98-86-2	Acetophenone	120,058	C8H8O	B	4,80
1232	103-11-7	Acrylic acid, 2-ethylhexyl ester	184,146	C11H20O2	A	3,44
1363	584-84-9	Benzene, 2,4-diisocyanato-1-methyl-	174,043	C9H6N2O2	B	32,16
1401	629-59-4	Tetradecane	198,235	C14H30	A	14,77
1463	5805-62-9	Benzimidazole, 5-tert-butyl-2-methyl-	188,131	C12H16N2	C	2,76
1505	1133-72-8	1,3-Indandione, 2-acetyl-	188,047	C11H8O3	C	5,07
1517	96-76-4	2,4-Di-tert-butylphenol	206,167	C14H22O	A	10,91
1521	128-37-0	Butylated Hydroxytoluene	220,183	C15H24O	A	5,89
1580	4098-71-9	Isophorone diisocyanate	222,137	C12H18N2O2	B	12,52
1594	629-73-2	1-Hexadecene	224,250	C16H32	B	3,21
1601	544-76-3	Hexadecane	226,266	C16H34	A	26,34
1605	4098-71-9	Isophorone diisocyanate	222,137	C12H18N2O2	B	34,73
1649	6607-34-7	Cyclic DEG+AA	216,100	C10H16O5	A	4,29
1695	1520-44-1	1,3-Diphenylbutane	210,141	C16H18	C	2,49
1701	629-78-7	Heptadecane	240,282	C17H36	A	2,59
1733	65189-90-4	Benzenemethanol, .alpha.-methyl-4-phenyl-	212,120	C15H16O	C	2,86
1766	20071-09-4	trans-1,2-Diphenylcyclobutane / Styrene diisocyanate	208,125	C16H16	A	6,98
1794	7206-19-1	3-Octadecene, (E)-	252,282	C18H36	B	3,65
1801	593-45-3	Octadecane	254,297	C18H38	A	26,54
1888	3886-80-4	Acetamide, N-dodecyl-	227,225	C14H29NO	C	6,29
1932	82304-66-3	7,9-Di-tert-butyl-1-oxaspiro(4,5)deca-6,9-diene	276,173	C17H24O3	A	18,73
1965	57-10-3	n-Hexadecanoic acid	256,240	C16H32O2	A	8,13
1969	84-74-2	Dibutyl phthalate / DBP	278,152	C16H22O4	B	4,12
2001	112-95-8	Eicosane	282,329	C20H42	A	23,48
2143	112-80-1	Oleic Acid	282,256	C18H34O2	B	7,24
2166	57-11-4	Octadecanoic acid	284,272	C18H36O2	A	12,57
2201	629-97-0	Docosane	310,360	C22H46	A	17,28
2267	77-90-7	Acetyl tributyl citrate / ATBC	402,225	C20H34O8	A	3,01
2278	629-96-9	1-Eicosanol	298,324	C20H42O	B	2,25
2395	10192-32-2	1-Tetracosene	336,376	C24H48	B	4,04
2401	646-31-1	Tetracosane	338,391	C24H50	A	12,65
2499	1000465-48-0	(Z)-Docos-9-enenitrile	319,324	C22H41N	C	3,53
2560	1000314-57-9	Carbonic acid, pentadecyl phenyl ester	348,266	C22H36O3	C	3,44
2578	10586-57-9	11E-Eicosenamide	309,303	C20H39NO	C	8,69
2601	630-01-3	Hexacosane	366,423	C26H54	A	18,03
2666	1000314-58-0	Carbonic acid, hexadecyl phenyl ester	362,282	C23H38O3	C	2,56
2795	112-84-5	13Z-Docosenamide / Erucamide	337,334	C22H43NO	A	167,20
2801	630-02-4	Octacosane	394,454	C28H58	A	13,16
2832	//	Cyclic DEG+PG+2AA	402,189	C19H30O9	B	5,23
2837	7683-64-9	Supraene	410,391	C30H50	B	5,85
2848	//	Cyclic 2NPG+2AA	428,241	C22H36O8	C	5,47
2963	119-13-1	.delta.-Tocopherol	402,350	C27H46O2	B	5,32
2974	14167-67-0	Nonacosane, 3-methyl-	422,485	C30H62	C	3,53
3000	638-68-6	Triacontane	422,485	C30H62	A	9,91
3119	//	Cyclic 2DEG+2AA	432,200	C20H32O10	B	5,98
3200	544-85-4	Dotriacontane	450,516	C32H66	A	4,04
3401	14167-59-0	Tetratriacontane	478,548	C34H70	A	3,73
3456	31570-04-4	Tris(2,4-di-tert-butylphenyl) phosphite / Irgafos	646,451	C42H63O3P	A	277,93
3637	2082-79-3	Octadecyl 3-(3,5-di-tert-butyl-4-hydroxyphenyl) phosphate / Irgafos	530,470	C35H62O3	A	255,87
3646	95906-11-9	Tri(2,4-di-tert-butyl phenyl) phosphate / Irgafos	662,446	C42H63O4P	A	256,74

Table 11: GC-MS/FID data of molecules detected in sample PIRM00655 (CFP00241), a 100% mono-film produced from CFP00219

DB-5 RI	CAS	Chemical name	Exact Mol. Weight	Molecular formula	GC Confidence Index	µg/g material
1492		BHA external standard				
1400	629-59-4	Tetradecane	198,235	C14H30	A	2,72
1475	719-22-2	2,5-Cyclohexadiene-1,4-dione, 2,6-bis(1,1-dimethyl-2-propenyl)-	220,146	C14H20O2	B	2,18
1503	112-18-5	1-Dodecanamine, N,N-dimethyl-	213,246	C14H31N	B	6,09
1515	96-76-4	2,4-Di-tert-butylphenol	206,167	C14H22O	A	5,37
1592	629-73-2	1-Hexadecene	224,250	C16H32	B	2,69
1600	544-76-3	Hexadecane	226,266	C16H34	A	15,72
1700	629-78-7	Heptadecane	240,282	C17H36	A	3,51
1705	112-75-4	1-Tetradecanamine, N,N-dimethyl-	241,277	C16H35N	B	22,02
1793	112-88-9	1-Octadecene	252,282	C18H36	B	6,67
1800	593-45-3	Octadecane	254,297	C18H38	A	27,12
1845	35936-85-7	Dodecanamide, N-ethyl-	227,225	C14H29NO	C	3,00
1883	36653-82-4	1-Hexadecanol	242,261	C16H34O	B	72,18
1900	629-92-5	Nonadecane	268,313	C19H40	A	13,38
1908	112-69-6	Dimethyl palmitamine	269,308	C18H39N	B	104,72
1927	112-39-0	Hexadecanoic acid, methyl ester	270,256	C17H34O2	B	16,21
1930	82304-66-3	7,9-Di-tert-butyl-1-oxaspiro(4,5)deca-6,9-diene	276,173	C17H24O3	A	3,60
1950	6386-38-5	Benzenepropanoic acid, 3,5-bis(1,1-dimethyl-2-propenyl)-	292,204	C18H28O3	A	2,12
1965	57-10-3	n-Hexadecanoic acid	256,240	C16H32O2	A	18,54
2000	112-95-8	Eicosane	282,329	C20H42	A	21,42
2052	3015-65-4	N,N-Dimethyltetradecanamide	255,256	C16H33NO	B	2,04
2064	6418-46-8	Eicosane, 3-methyl-	296,344	C21H44	B	3,53
2087	112-92-5	1-Octadecanol	270,292	C18H38O	B	81,39
2100	629-94-7	Heneicosane	296,344	C21H44	A	2,62
2107	124-28-7	Dimantine	297,340	C20H43N	B	13,94
2129	112-61-8	Methyl stearate	298,287	C19H38O2	B	24,29
2144	101-77-9	4,4'-methylene dianiline (MDA) (T)	198,116	C13H14N2	A	6,76
2151	25117-37-7	Heneicosane, 5-methyl-	310,360	C22H46	B	3,44
2167	57-11-4	Octadecanoic acid	284,272	C18H36O2	A	28,84
2194	1599-67-3	1-Docosene	308,344	C22H44	B	3,44
2200	629-97-0	Docosane	310,360	C22H46	A	17,49
2259	3886-91-7	N,N-dimethyl hexadecanamide	283,288	C18H37NO	A	14,07
2263	6864-37-5	Dicyclohexylmethane, 3,3'-dimethyl 4,4'-diaminodiphenyl-	238,241	C15H30N2	B	4,33
2295	141-24-2	9-Octadecenoic acid, 12-hydroxy-, methyl ester	312,266	C19H36O3	B	3,68
2335	2136-72-3	Ethanol, 2-(octadecyloxy)-	314,318	C20H42O2	C	29,98
2394	10192-32-2	1-Tetracosene	336,376	C24H48	B	1,93
2400	646-31-1	Tetracosane	338,391	C24H50	A	11,19
2445	111-60-4	Octadecanoic acid, 2-hydroxyethyl ester	328,298	C20H40O3	C	2,46
2500	629-99-2	Pentacosane	352,407	C25H52	A	3,23
2600	630-01-3	Hexacosane	366,423	C26H54	A	13,20
2677	35820-56-6	3-Methylhexacosane	380,438	C27H56	B	2,65
2689	6703-82-8	Cyclopentane, heneicosyl-	364,407	C26H52	B	5,88
2785	112-84-5	13Z-Docosamide / Erucamide	337,334	C22H43NO	A	6,35
2799	630-02-4	Octacosane	394,454	C28H58	A	7,32
2836	7683-64-9	Supraene	410,391	C30H50	B	4,41
2950	71868-29-6	5-Methylnonacosane	422,485	C30H62	B	2,75
2999	638-68-6	Triacontane	422,485	C30H62	A	7,09
3199	544-85-4	Dotriacontane	450,516	C32H66	A	3,56
3468	31570-04-4	Tris(2,4-di-tert-butylphenyl) phosphite / Irga	646,451	C42H63O3P	A	1 402,31
3535	110729-26-5	Benzenepropanoic acid, 3-tert-butyl 4-hydroxyphenyl ester	474,407	C31H54O3	A	7,85
3661	2082-79-3	Octadecyl 3-(3,5-di-tert-butyl-4-hydroxyphenyl) phosphate / Irga	530,470	C35H62O3	A	2 203,87
3664	95906-11-9	Tri(2,4-di-tert-butyl phenyl) phosphate / Irga	662,446	C42H63O4P	A	581,93

Table 12: LC-HRMS/CAD data of molecules detected in sample PIRM00651 (CFP00219) entering the mechanical recycling / processing cascade

Ret.Time min	CAS	Chemical name	Exact Mol. Weight	Molecular formula	LC Schyman ski Index	Extraction µg/g materi
9,9	1167572-53-3	PPG n5	308,21989	C15H32O6	2	6,81
10,8	314254-68-7	Cyclic 2DEG+2AA	432,19955	C20H32O10	3	4,07
11,8	//	Cyclic DEG+PG+2AA	402,18899	C19H30O9	2	3,27
11,8	42966-30-3	Magnesium caprate	366,26206	C20H38MgO4	3	3,27
13,1	112-18-5	N,N-dimethyldodecan-1-amine	213,24565	C14H31N	2	3,49
13,4	//	Cyclic 3DEG+3AA	648,29933	C30H48O15	2	13,02
13,4	69039-85-6	PPG n7	424,30362	C21H44O8	2	13,02
15,7	//	PPG n9	540,38735	C27H56O10	3	8,33
16,8	70191-76-3	Disodium dihexadecyl diphenyl	824,46714	C44H74Na2O7	3	13,81
19,1	//	PPG n14	830,59668	C42H86O15	3	3,44
19,6	//	PPG n15	888,63854	C45H92O16	3	8,35
20,0	//	PPG n16	946,68041	C48H98O17	3	20,46
20,3	629-54-9	Hexadecanamide	255,25621	C16H33NO	1	21,09
20,3	//	PPG n17	1004,72227	C51H104O18	3	21,09
20,6	301-02-0	Oleamide	281,27186	C18H35NO	2	21,23
20,6	//	PPG n18	1062,76414	C54H110O19	3	21,23
20,9	//	PPG n19	1120,80600	C57H116O20	3	23,06
21,2	124-26-5	Octadecanamide	283,28751	C18H37NO	1	26,10
21,2	//	PPG n20	1178,84787	C60H122O21	3	26,10
21,5	//	PPG n21	1236,88973	C63H128O22	3	32,62
21,5	13393-93-6	1-Phenanthrenemethanol, tetrac	292,27662	C20H36O	3	32,62
21,6	5806-72-4	2,4-Di-tert-octyl phenol	318,29227	C22H38O	3	21,14
22,2	112-84-5	13Z-Docosanamide / Erucamide	337,33446	C22H43NO	1	75,13
22,7	3061-75-4	Docosanamide	339,35011	C22H45NO	1	4,19
22,8	//	Tetracosanamide	365,36576	C24H47NO	3	6,14
23,3	//	Tetracosanamide	367,38141	C24H49NO	3	2,82
23,9	2540-54-7	Glycerol triricinoleate	932,76804	C57H104O9	3	10,42
23,9	6683-19-8	Irganox 1010 / Pentaerytritol tet	1176,78408	C73H108O12	2	10,42
24,3	2082-79-3	Octadecyl 3-(3,5-di-tert-butyl-4	530,46990	C35H62O3	1	23,16
24,3	95906-11-9	Tri(2,4-di-tert-butyl phenyl) pho	662,44640	C42H63O4P	1	23,16
24,9	31570-04-4	Tris(2,4-di-tert-butylphenyl) pho	646,45148	C42H63O3P	1	6,17

Table 13: LC-HRMS/CAD data of molecules detected in sample PIMRM00655 (CFP00241,) a 100% mono-film produced from CFP00219

Ret.Time min	CAS	Chemical name	Exact Mol. Weight	Molecular formula	LC Schymans ki Index	Extraction c
						µg/g materi
1,0	101-77-9	4,4'-methylene dianiline (MDA) (T	198,11570	C13H14N2	1	15,30
4,7	1131-16-4	3,5-Dimethyl-1-phenylpyrazole	172,10005	C11H12N2	3	NQ
4,9	4792-15-8	Pentaethylene glycol / PEG n5	238,14164	C10H22O6	1	NQ
5,5	52578-32-2	2-hydroxy-3-methyl-4H-pyrido[1,2	176,05858	C9H8N2O2	3	NQ
5,6	2615-15-8	Hexaethylene glycol / PEG n6	282,16786	C12H26O7	1	11,91
5,9	442-51-3	Harmine	212,09496	C13H12N2O	3	2,38
6,3	5117-19-1	Octaethylene glycol / PEG n8	370,22029	C16H34O9	1	2,58
7,3	959-26-2	Terephthalic acid, di(2-hydroxyet	254,07904	C12H14O6	2	11,34
7,4	6809-70-7	Undecaethylene glycol / PEG n11	502,29893	C22H46O12	1	NQ
9,0	6812-36-8	Hexadecaethylene glycol / PEG n	722,43001	C32H66O17	1	NQ
11,8	42966-30-3	Magnesium caprate	366,26206	C20H38MgO	3	2,48
11,8	84-66-2	Diethyl phthalate	222,08921	C12H14O4	1	2,48
12,4	//	Linear 3EG+2PA	446,12130	C22H22O10	2	12,36
13,4	112-18-5	N,N-dimethyldodecan-1-amine	213,24565	C14H31N	2	17,17
13,4	69039-85-6	PPG n7	424,30362	C21H44O8	2	17,17
13,7	29278-57-7	Cyclic DEG+EG+2TPA	428,11074	C22H20O9	3	3,17
14,6	//	PPG n8	482,34549	C24H50O9	2	31,29
15,3	//	Linear 2DEG+3PA	638,16356	C32H30O14	2	1,92
15,7	//	PPG n9	540,38735	C27H56O10	3	24,15
16,4	1620-98-0	3,5-di-tert-Butyl-4-hydroxybenza	234,16198	C15H22O2	2	NQ
16,5	//	PPG n10	598,42922	C30H62O11	2	NQ
16,6	124-30-1	Octadecanamine	269,30825	C18H39N	2	29,00
16,8	17678-60-3	N,N-Dimethyl-1-pentadecanamine	255,29260	C17H37N	3	NQ
17,4	//	PPG n11	656,47108	C33H68O12	2	22,67
17,4	//	Cyclic 3EG+3PA	576,12678	C30H24O12	3	22,67
18,1	//	PPG n12	714,51295	C36H74O13	3	29,48
18,4	638-58-4	Tetradecanamide	227,22491	C14H29NO	2	NQ
18,5	//	PPG n13	772,55481	C39H80O14	3	8,07
18,7	//	PPG n13	772,55481	C39H80O14	3	6,84
19,0	638-58-4	Tetradecanamide	227,22491	C14H29NO	2	19,82
19,0	60-33-3	Linoleic acid	280,24023	C18H32O2	3	19,82
19,1	//	PPG n14	830,59668	C42H86O15	3	7,61
19,6	//	PPG n15	888,63854	C45H92O16	3	8,85
19,9	629-54-9	Hexadecanamide	255,25621	C16H33NO	1	10,04
19,9	//	PPG n16	946,68041	C48H98O17	3	10,04
20,3	//	PPG n17	1004,72227	C51H104O18	3	9,71
20,3	629-54-9	Hexadecanamide	255,25621	C16H33NO	1	9,71
20,7	//	PPG n18	1062,76414	C54H110O19	3	15,31
20,7	36913-60-7	2,2-Bis(hydroxymethyl)-1,3-propa	656,42882	C39H60O8	3	15,31
20,9	//	PPG n19	1120,80600	C57H116O21	3	8,61
20,9	124-26-5	Octadecanamide	283,28751	C18H37NO	1	8,61
21,1	//	PPG n20	1178,84787	C60H122O22	3	21,69
21,4	//	PPG n21	1236,88973	C63H128O23	3	6,92
21,4	13393-93-6	1-Phenanthrenemethanol, tetradec	292,27662	C20H36O	3	6,92
21,9	51360-63-5	Eicosanamide	311,31881	C20H41NO	3	NQ
22,2	112-84-5	13Z-Docosanamide / Erucamide	337,33446	C22H43NO	1	15,71
22,3	119-07-3	Octyl decyl phthalate	418,30831	C26H42O4	2	NQ
22,7	84633-54-5	Pentaerythritol tris[3-(3,5-di-terti	916,60645	C56H84O10	2	11,32
22,7	3061-75-4	Docosanamide	339,35011	C22H45NO	1	11,32
23,3	33368-87-5	1,2,3-Propanetriol 1,3-dioctanoate	498,39204	C29H54O6	2	ND
23,9	2540-54-7	Glycerol triricinoleate	932,76804	C57H104O9	3	15,51
23,9	6683-19-8	Irganox 1010 / Pentaerythritol tetra	1176,78408	C73H108O11	2	15,51
24,3	2082-79-3	Octadecyl 3-(3,5-di-tert-butyl-4-h	530,46990	C35H62O3	1	70,62
24,3	95906-11-9	Tri(2,4-di-tert-butyl phenyl) phosph	662,44640	C42H63O4P	1	70,62
24,9	31570-04-4	Tris(2,4-di-tert-butylphenyl) phosph	646,45148	C42H63O3P	1	15,88

d. ICP-MS (Fraunhofer) analysis for inorganic component

For evaluating the removal of printing ink/tracer components (inorganic components), various samples from loop 3 (cycle 1), loop 3 (cycle 2) and loop 2 were investigated. The input material for loop 3 consisted of tracer marked food packs. Consequently, the loop 3 material was used to track the tracer components Yttrium (Y), Holmium (Ho) and Ytterbium (Yb) through the recycling treatments. In addition, the elements Titanium (Ti) and Copper (Cu) were chosen as representatives of printing ink components in order to follow the deinking efficiency. The loop 2 material (B2B collected post-consumer food packs) was also investigated for Ti and Cu as printing ink components.

The sample material was subject to acidic digestion using nitric acid (69 %). The obtained solution was diluted and subsequently analysed by ICP-MS. Quantification was performed by external calibration. The limit of quantification was 1 mg/kg in the material.

For the ICP-MS analysis, the following treatment steps were evaluated:

Table 14: *Sample flow for inorganic components; "Water-based Deinking – Mechanical Recycling – Deodorisation" Cascade on Loop 3 (Cycle 1) material*

Sample code	Description	Analyzed elements
CFP00141 (reference, C ₀)	Shredded laminate (as input waste) for Loop 3 Cycle 1 (flakes)	Ti, Cu, Y, Yb, Ho
CFP00219	WP6 Loop 3 Cycle 1 washed + shredded (flakes)	
CFP00216	WP6 Loop 3 Cycle 1 washed + shredded + deinked (flakes)	
CFP00220	Material after additivition and granulation (granulate)	
CFP00234	Material after deodorization (granulate)	

Table 15: *Sample flow for inorganic components for the deinking process on Loop 3 (Cycle 2) material*

Sample code	Description	Analyzed elements
CFP00235 (reference, C ₀)	Loop 3 Cycle 2 input film for Hydrodyn	Ti, Cu, Y, Yb, Ho
CFP00298	Flakes after deinking at Hydrodyn	

Table 16: Sample flow for inorganic components; Solvent-based Recycling on Loop 3 (Cycle 1) material

Sample code	Description	Analyzed elements
CFP00147 (reference, C ₀)	"contaminated CFP00141"* laminate Loop 3 Cycle 1 (CFP00141; flakes)	Ti, Cu, Y, Yb, Ho
CFP00182	Material after solvent-based recycling (pellets)	

* "contaminated" by the filling with coffee (emptied packs were used for the analysis)

Table 17: Sample flow for inorganic components; "Water-based Deinking – Mechanical Recycling – Deodorisation" Cascade on Loop 2 material

Sample	Description	Analyzed elements
CFP00262 (reference, C ₀)	Loop 2 Input 10 mm (flakes)	Ti, Cu
Sample 11	Variant 1, Rinsing by Hydrodyn (Step 3; flakes)	
Sample 13	Variant 1, After densification at Suez (granulate)	
Sample 14	Variant 1, After granulation at Suez (granulate)*	
CFP00263 (reference, C ₀)	Loop 2, Cycle 1 Input 20 mm (flakes)	
Sample 18	Variant 2, Rinsing by Hydrodyn (Step 3; flakes)	
Sample 20	Variant 2, After densification at Suez (granulate)	
Sample 21	Variant 2, After granulation at Suez (granulate)*	

*The deodorization step was not investigated for this cascade as it is not expected to have an impact on the concentration of non-volatile inorganic compounds.

The following tables list the obtained reduction efficiency for the analysed elements and processes referenced to the corresponding C₀ – samples as given above.

Table 18: Reduction efficiency in % for "Water-based Deinking – Mechanical Recycling – Deodorisation" Cascade on Loop 3 (Cycle 1) material

Element		Ti	Cu	Y	Ho	Yb
Reduction Efficiency		[%]	[%]	[%]	[%]	[%]
Referred to CFP00141; C ₀	CFP00219	4.7	28.7	56.5	52.2	60.5
	CFP00216	89.8	94.6	98.7	98.6	98.8
	CFP00220	53.7	88.7	91.5	90.7	92.3
	CFP00234	42.0	90.4	91.3	90.6	92.2

Table 19: Reduction efficiency in % for the deinking step on Loop 3 (Cycle 2) material

Element		Ti	Cu	Y	Ho	Yb
Reduction efficiency		[%]	[%]	[%]	[%]	[%]
Referred to CFP00235; C _o	CFP00298	70.8	96.1	> 99	> 99	>99

For the calculation of the reduction efficiency of the deinking step on the Loop 3 Cycle 2 material only the elements' concentrations in the printing ink applied onto the L3C2 laminate was considered as only these amounts were accessible for the deinking process. The total concentration of the elements in the laminate structure of CFP00235 was higher due to the fact that the inner PE-PCR layer was made of the project PCR obtained from Loop3 Cycle 1 (L3C1), which contained residual levels of the above elements. A detailed explanation can additionally be found in D3.7.

Table 20: Reduction efficiency in % for "Solvent-based Recycling" on Loop 3 (Cycle 1) material

Element		Ti	Cu	Y	Ho	Yb
Reduction efficiency		[%]	[%]	[%]	[%]	[%]
Referred to CFP00147; C _o	CFP00182	97.7	90.9	99.2	99.2	99.3

Table 21: Reduction efficiency in % for “Deinking – Mechanical Recycling – Deodorisation” Cascade on Loop 2 material

Element	Reduction Efficiency	
	Ti	Cu
	[%]	[%]
Referred to CFP00262; C ₀		
Sample 11	59.7	41.9
Sample 13	46.1	42.7
Sample 14	49.5	45.3
Referred to CFP00263, C ₀		
Sample 18	80.0	84.0
Sample 20	75.6	78.6
Sample 21	76.3	76.2

The reduction efficiencies given in bold mark the endpoints of the investigated steps. Consequently, these values represent the reduction efficiency for the overall process for the investigated elements.

e. Bioassay for mutagenicity: Ames test (Nestle)

An aliquot of 1.5 mL of the hexane/acetone extracts used for the NIAS/IAS screening (see above) of samples CFP00219 and CFP00241 was prepared the same way as described in Section 2.d.

Focus of the bioassays performed was mutagenicity as such effect should not be present in packaging materials. Recently, a study appeared where mutagenicity was observed in mechanical recycling of polyolefins (Mayrhofer et al. 2023²). A hypothesis for the mutagenicity observed was that N-nitrosamines may be formed from the thermally unstable nitrocellulose printing inks under processing conditions such as mechanical recycling. This was however never confirmed.

To understand whether the printed laminate films subjected to mechanical recycling may induce mutagenicity, two samples were tested with the Ames assay. The first sample was CFP00219, i.e. flakes from printed monomaterial laminate produced in CIRCULAR FoodPack before mechanical recycling and the second sample was CFP00241, the recylate produced via deinking, after mechanical recycling and deodorization. Two strains were used (TA-98 and TA-100) both with and without S9 metabolic activation.

Table 22 shows the results of the Ames tests highlighting that sample CFP00241 after mechanical recycling was positive for strain TA98 in presence of metabolic activation. This is in line with Mayrhofer et al 2023² who demonstrated that 36 of the 89 samples tested (HDPE, LDPE, PET, PP, and PS) were positive for the same strain. The other strains were mostly negative.

Table 22: AMES TA-98 and TA-100 strain results with and without S9 metabolic activation.

Nestlé sample ID	Fraunhofer sample ID	Strain TA98 -S9	Strain TA98 +S9	Strain TA100 -S9	Strain TA100 +S9
PIRM00651	CFP00219	Negative	Negative	Negative	Negative
PIRM00655	CFP00241	Negative	Positive	Negative	Negative

The reason for this effect remains unknown and will probably not be identified with the generic NIAS screening methodologies above. According to Mayrhofer et al. 2023 PAA's or N-nitrosamines may be formed which are typically present at trace level that fall below the limit of detection (LoD) of generic screening methods. Fractionation in combination with targeted methods would be needed to understand the origin of the mutagenic effects.

According to Mayrhofer et al. 2023², nitrocellulose printing inks may be a source of the mutagenicity. However, the samples tested in the present work were not printed with nitrocellulose printing inks. Therefore, the cause of the mutagenic effects remains to be further investigated, especially for printed structures using printing inks other than nitrocellulose.

f. Saturated and unsaturated hydrocarbons incl. mineral oil (Nestle)

The samples along the mechanical recycling cascade were investigated for the presence of saturated and unsaturated hydrocarbons including mineral oils and POSH using LC-GC-FID. Figure 16 and Figure 17 show the chromatograms for the saturated hydrocarbon (typically POSH) and unsaturated hydrocarbon fraction. The amount of saturated and unsaturated hydrocarbons detected is shown in Table 23.

The saturated hydrocarbon fraction shows a regular pattern of peaks indicative for POSH. These POSH riding peaks were included in the semi-quantification results shown in Table 23. The values in Table 23 are ranked to follow the recycling process. Clear is that the deinking/drying step does not impact the amount of POSH detected. On the other hand, the densification, degassing, additivation, granulation etc (performed by Suez) seem to remove saturated hydrocarbons, most probably POSH. The unsaturated hydrocarbons (olefins?) were removed as well. The deodorisation by Kreyenborg does not seem to further reduce the amount of POSH. During the following extrusion tests, new POSH are formed most probably by degradation of the polymeric chains into small pieces. Note that from sample CFP00242 onwards another source of PE PCR (commercial PE PCR in mixture with project PE PCR) was used and therefore, a comparison with the previous samples should not be performed.

Figure 16: LC-GC-FID Chromatogram focusing on the saturated hydrocarbon fraction

Figure 17: LC-GC-FID Chromatogram focusing on the unsaturated hydrocarbon fraction

Table 23: Saturated and unsaturated hydrocarbons detected in the various materials of the investigated cascade.

Nestle sample ID	Fraunhofer sample ID	Saturated hydrocarbons (mg/kg)	Unsaturated hydrocarbons (mg/kg)
PIRM00651	CFP00219	660	18
PIRM00647	CFP00216	741	33
PIRM00649	CFP00217	196	2
PIRM00652	CFP00220	115	<2
PIRM00654	CFP00234	178	<2
PIRM00655	CFP00241	746	25
PIRM00656	CFP00242	177	15
PIRM00657	CFP00243	814	58
PIRM00658	CFP00244	545	23
PIRM00659	CFP00245	734	21

4. DISCUSSION

As an overall conclusion, the obtained data on the chemical purity, biological activity and reduction efficiencies of the printing inks (based on marker elements of used pigments) showed that the investigated treatment steps and technologies are not yet sufficient to clean the polyolefins so that these can be used in food contact materials. The rationale for this is summarized below.

The possibilities that the use of functional barriers could offer for the integration of PCR PE into laminate structures are discussed in D4.6.

a. Characterization of the input material / waste characterizations

The Nestlé sample preparation procedure revealed more chemical information compared to the Fraunhofer sample preparation procedure and was therefore used in the current work. The chemical and biological screening of the PE samples (washed and shredded flakes of real waste) showed that these materials were highly contaminated both in the food grade and non-food grade PE waste resin:

- POSH and most probably mineral oils (MOSH and MOAH) were detected.
- Various contaminants were detected that are typically not found in food contact materials.
- Mutagenicity was observed, which has a direct impact on Article 3 of Regulation (EC) No 1935/2004 regarding safety.

The quality of the PE in flexible household packaging waste samples investigated is thus poor and disqualifies these samples for the use in direct food contact applications. Only in case recycling processes would enable the removal of these contaminants, direct food contact

applications could be considered. When using this material behind functional barriers, the quality must still significantly improve as safety concerns cannot be excluded (especially related to the mutagenicity detected).

b. Characterization and monitoring of recyclates' quality through the recycling and re-use process steps

The aim of the performed experiments was to characterize and monitor the quality of the recyclate through the different recycling treatments. Especially in the case of recycling materials, the different treatment processes or steps may impact the material composition and thus the variety of substances that might be transferred onto food when used in food contact applications. Polyolefins are known to degrade during processing and recycling, which leads to an increase of low molecular weight substances. Degradation/reaction products of the polymer itself or of stabilizers added during production or recycling may be present in the material as a result of decomposition and chemical reactions. In addition, recycled materials may contain contaminants from the environment or filled goods and also substances that might be introduced through the recycling process.

With respect to organic substances, non-target screening analyses were performed by means of headspace GC-MS and GC-FID/MS with liquid injection following an extraction of the sample material.

The non-target screening analyses are designed to cover a wide variety of chemical compounds. However, it has to be noted that the performed analyses, as screening analyses in general, are not capable of detecting any compound at a high sensitivity.

The analysis by headspace gas chromatography allows the identification of volatile substances that are present in the material. The main headspace components of sample CFP00241⁶ were identified as 2-methyl 1 propene (isobutene), acetic acid ethenyl ester (vinyl acetate) as well as alkanes and aldehydes. Alkanes and aldehydes can be formed as a result of thermal stress and oxidation of the polymer⁷. Furthermore, phosphoric acid, tris(2-ethylhexyl) ester was detected, which might be related to a phosphite-type antioxidant.

The screening analyses performed by GC and HPLC for semi-volatile and non-volatile substances revealed that various molecules, which were present in the input material (CFP00219), were removed during recycling. These molecules were:

- Two different isocyanates which could originate from adhesives or the printing ink used. It should be noted that these molecules can be formed as analytical artifact in the GC-injector and should be further investigated.
- Various volatile molecules such as benzaldehyde and acetophenone.
- Some cyclic polyester oligomers made of diethylene glycol, adipic acid and propylene glycol PG.

⁶ Extruded monofilm sample with 100% PE PCR of Loop3 Cycle 1 of the project, PE PCR produced by washing/shredding/deinking/delamination/mechanical recycling/deodorization

⁷ Bradley, E., Coulier, L., 2007: An investigation into the reaction and breakdown products from starting substances used to produce food contact plastics. FD07/01

Various molecules that were not present in the input material (CFP00219) were detected after the recycling steps. The main highlights are:

- A primary aromatic amine (PAA). PAA's should be non-detectable in the packaged food. Targeted analysis for PAA should be performed to rule out any migration of PAAs.
- A series of aliphatic amines are detected only in the material after recycling such as 1-Tetradecanamine, N,N-dimethyl- (CAS 112-75-4) by GC-MS and N,N-Dimethyl-1-pentadecanamine (CAS 17678-60-3) by LC-HRMS. The most likely source of this series of aliphatic amines is the detergent used in the mechanical recycling process (hexadecyltrimethyl ammonium bromide, CAS 57-09-0). The amount of these molecules by LC-HRMS/CAD could not be estimated as these ionic molecules do not give a response on the CAD detector which was used for semi-quantification in this work. Semi-quantification could be performed by GC-MS/FID.
- Polyethylene glycol oligomers and oligomers consisting of ethylene glycol, diethylene glycol, terephthalic acid and isophthalic acid were detected.

The experiments performed clearly highlight that especially the more volatile NIAS are removed during the recycling process, whereas a few others may be introduced. In addition, saturated and unsaturated hydrocarbons including POSH are removed during the recycling steps, but new POSH is formed when the recycled resin is extruded.

Using bioassays, mutagenicity was observed in the sample after recycling (CFP00241) aligned with what has been reported in literature. A cause for this effect was not found so far and needs further investigations.

It has to be outlined that the data obtained within the performed screening analyses are used to set up a database of contaminants in recycled polyolefins. Consequently, an in-depth overview over substances detected in the performed non-target screening analyses is given in Deliverable 4.5 "Database of contaminants in recycled polyolefins".

In addition, the (semi-)quantification results on substances contained in the recycled material served as a basis to calculate the theoretical migration into food taking into account the barrier properties of the laminate structure as evaluated within Task 4.5. This is reported in Deliverable 4.6 "Verification of barrier concept for the final demonstrator".

c. Evaluation of the deinking efficiency

For evaluating the removal of inorganic printing ink/tracer components, various samples from loop 3 (cycle 1) und loop 2 were investigated for Ti and Cu as inorganic representatives of the printing ink and Y, Yb, Ho as representatives of the tracers that were integrated in the ink. The inorganic components were analysed by ICP-MS (a specific analysis for the respective organic components was not done). From the results of the ICP-MS measurements, the following can be concluded:

- **Loop 3 (cycle 1) material:** for the removal of Cu and the tracer elements, the determined reduction efficiencies were in the range of 90 % for the "Water-based Deinking – Mechanical Recycling – Deodorisation" Cascade. For Ti, the reduction rate was significantly lower with 40 % (Table 18). The reason for this remains unclear, a possible introduction / contamination of titanium in the workup process after deinking cannot be completely ruled

out. With the “solvent-based recycling process” reduction efficiencies up to 99 % could be achieved (Table 20).

- **Loop 3 (cycle 2) material:** for the removal of copper (Cu) the determined reduction efficiencies were in the range of 96 %, for the tracer elements in the range of 99 %, Consequently, the achieved reduction efficiencies were significantly improved for the optimized deinking process performed on the cycle 2 material at the subcontractor Hydrodyn compared to cycle 1.
- **Loop 2 material:** Two different flakes sizes were used as input materials of the investigated “Water-based Deinking – Mechanical Recycling – Deodorisation” cascade. Generally, the reduction efficiency was higher for the larger flakes (20 mm). An overall reduction efficiency of up to 76 % was achieved for the investigated elements Cu and Ti (Table 21) as markers for pigments and printing ink components.
- As an overall conclusion, the obtained data on the reduction efficiencies showed that the investigated treatment steps and technologies are not yet sufficient to achieve the envisaged > 99.5 % ink removal (based on the analysis of the inorganic ink components titanium and copper). It should be noted that titanium and copper (respectively the related pigments) were selected as marker substances for printing inks, but not for toxicological reasons. The related pigments are authorized for the use in printing inks for food contact applications.

